

Appendices D-E of

The elderly among the oldest: new evidence for extremely metal-poor RR Lyrae stars

Appendix D: Orbits

We estimated the space velocity components and Galactic orbit parameters of the three EMP stars using the Python package `galpy` (Bovy et al. 2015). To perform calculation of the orbits, we adopted the McMillan (2017) Galactic potential and we integrated the initial conditions forward for 10 Gyr with steps of 1 Myr.

The resulting orbits, in the Galactocentric reference frame, are shown in Fig.D.2-D.4.

HD331986: the Galactic orbital parameters of this star suggest a status of a prograde disc star ($\lambda_Z \simeq 0.82$), probable an object of transition between thin- and thick-disc population ($Z_{max} \simeq 1.1$ kpc).

DO Hya: on the basis of its Galactic orbital parameters, DO Hya can be identified as a halo star ($Z_{max} \simeq 6.1$ kpc) with a retrograde orbit ($\lambda_Z \simeq -0.19$).

BPS CS 30317-056: the calculated Galactic orbital parameters provide a classification of this object as a halo star ($Z_{max} \simeq 6.1$ kpc) with a prograde orbit ($\lambda_Z \simeq 0.07$).

Appendix E: Spectral syntheses of Mg and Mn and Additional Elemental Abundances

In Figure E.1, we present the comparison between observed and synthetic spectra for HD 331986, DO Hya, and BPS CS 30317-056. The inferred $[X/Fe]$ ratios for Mg and Mn are displayed in each panel, alongside labels for the scrutinised lines. These values for the three EMP RRLs are given within the main manuscript. As previously emphasised, our goal was to derive consistent NLTE abundances for elements measured across all three sample stars and to compare these with literature values. Nevertheless, additional spectral features were detected in some of these stars; these additional elemental abundances are summarised in Table E.1, where we also specify whether NLTE grids were available or if we relied on the LTE assumption. Specifically, we report NLTE abundances for barium (lines at 4554, 4934 Å; Gallagher et al. 2020) and nickel (3807, 3858 Å; Bergemann et al. 2021, Voronov et al. 2022), while LTE abundances are provided for chromium (4254, 4274 Å) and scandium (4246, 4314, 4400 Å).

Table E.1. Additional element abundances. The average $[X/Fe]$ ratios are reported along with line-by-line scatter.

Star	$[Sc/Fe]_{II}$ LTE	$[Cr/Fe]_{I}$ LTE	$[Ni/Fe]_{I}$ NLTE	$[Ba/Fe]_{II}$ NLTE
HD 331986	—	—	—	—
DO Hya	0.61 ± 0.17	-0.23 ± 0.10	0.10 ± 0.10	—
BPS CS 30317-056	0.25 ± 0.02	-0.37 ± 0.05	-0.25 ± 0.05	-0.24 ± 0.10

Fig. D.1. Left – Circularity of the orbits as a function of the Galactocentric distance. The grey dots display RRLs belonging to our spectroscopic catalogue, while the red circles the three very metal-poor RRLs. Middle – same symbols as on the left, but here for the Toomre diagram Right – same symbols as on the left, but here for the Lindblad diagram.

Fig. D.2. The orbit of HD331986 in the Galactocentric reference frame calculated by using `galpy`. The upper panels show the orbit projected in the $X - Y$, $Z - Y$ and $X - Z$ planes, while the lower panel shows the orbit in the $R - Z$ plane, where R is the radial distance projected in the $X - Y$ plane. The blue symbol represents the present-day position and velocity vector. The orange circle in panel a) shows the position of the Sun.

Fig. D.3. The same as Figure D.2, but for DO Hya.

Fig. D.4. The same as Figure D.2, but for BPS CS 30317-056.

Fig. E.1. Comparison between observed and best-fit synthetic spectra for our sample RRLs for Mg I and Mn I lines.